

Effect of Changing Employee Readiness and Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance Through Work Stress on Employees of UPT. Food Plant Protection and Horticulture, North Sumatra

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine the readiness to change employees and OCB on employee performance through work stress on employees of the Technical Implementation Unit for Food Crops and Horticulture Protection (UPT PTPH) North Sumatra on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Pangkalan Masyur Medan City which is a government agency tasked with assisting the Head of Service in the implementation of administrative administration and/or technical duties of plant protection in the field of observation and control of Plant Destruction Organisms as well as observation and handling of Climate Change Impacts in all districts/cities. The results of the performance appraisal of UPT PTPH employees from 2019 to 2020 showed a decline. The decrease in employee performance is due to the lack of readiness to change employees in the face of change and OCB which is still less than employees and work stress. The sample used is 50 respondents with descriptive data analysis methods and SEM-PLS. The tool in analyzing the data is SmartPLS 3. The results obtained were readiness to change employees had a positive and significant effect on work stress, readiness to change employees had a positive and significant effect on job stress. significant effect on employee performance, OCB has a negative but not significant effect on work stress, OCB has a negative but not significant effect on employee performance, work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance, employee readiness to change has a negative and insignificant effect on performance through work stress and OCB positive but not significant effect on employee performance through work stress on employees of UPT PTPH North Sumatra.

Keywords: Readiness to change employees, OCB, work stress, employee performance.

I. Introduction

Today every company and agency is required to continue to experience development so that it can keep up with changes that continue to occur in the world. Developments that occur in the agency can be achieved by improving the performance of each employee. According to Khasmir (2016: 182) performance is the result and work behavior that has been achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period. In line with the opinion of Mangkunegara (2013: 67) performance is the result of work in terms of the quality and quantity of work that has been achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. So, performance is the result of the work of an employee in accordance with the targets set by the company both in terms of quality and quantity in a certain period.

Employee performance can be influenced by many variables. One of them is the readiness to change employees. According to Madsen, et al (2005), changes will continue to occur in an agency caused by several things including the rapid pace of global development, business risks, exciting opportunities, innovation, and a new leadership system. Employee readiness to change is a situation or condition of cognitive or even mental thinking of an employee that affects behavior, which is rejecting or supporting change (Armenakis, 1993). Holt, et al. (2007) state an individual's readiness to change as a comprehensive attitude that is simultaneously influenced by content (i.e., what is being changed), process (i.e., how the change is implemented), context (i.e., circumstances that are being changed), and the individual (i.e., what is being changed). , the characteristics of those who are asked to change) are involved. The role of employee readiness in accepting change is considered important. Therefore, an employee must have the readiness to change so that they can

continue to maintain their performance and even improve their performance and in achieving this performance, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is also needed.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has the meaning of organizational citizenship behavior. OCB is very important because formal job descriptions in roles during work cannot cover the entire set of behaviors required to achieve organizational goals (Somech & Oplatka: 2015). In the opinion of Hendrawan, et.al (2020), OCB itself has a meaning in the form of extra-role behavior or behavior that is outside the job description that has been previously set by the company that arises because of a prosocial attitude based on the personal sincerity of the employee.

Additional unwritten regulations can be in the form of employee behavior in carrying out their work in the agency to achieve agency success outside of the written job description, namely the willingness to cooperate, help each other, provide input, play an active role, provide extra services, and want to take advantage of their working time effectively. effective (Robbins & Judge, 2013). This is in line with the opinion of Kinicki and Fudgate (2013) that OCB behavior is very important for individuals to have in the company for two reasons, namely first, when individuals behave OCB it will be a positive value in the view of their colleagues and second, the more employees behave OCB will then provide positive feedback or results for the agency or company where the employee works. Furthermore, according to Hendrawan (2020) that the higher OCB owned by employees will be able to reduce the level of work stress on employees so that organizational goals will be achieved, namely with optimal performance of employees towards the organization because stress which is the cause of disease can decrease. Therefore, an agency must still be able to build OCB behavior in its employees so that it can support increasing employee performance and can be free from work stress faced while working in the agency.

Employee performance is also influenced by work stress experienced by employees. Job stress is a depressed state felt by an employee who works for a company or agency. According to Robbins and Judge (2017) that stress is a person's unpleasant psychological process that occurs as a response to pressure from the environment. Working in an agency also requires stress, but not all stress experienced by employees will be able to improve performance at work. so that work stress needs to be considered by the agency so that employees do not cause harm to the agency. According to Muslim (2020), stress is a response from a person to adjust to ongoing demands, where demands can be in the form of existing facts or new things that may occur but are understood to actually occur or actually. According to Sinambela in Sunyoto (2012) said that although stress is considered to have a bad influence, but it certainly depends on the individual in responding to any problems or stress. Job stress is a challenge for employees that must be overcome in their work. According to Deng, et.al (2019), stress arising from challenges positively affects work performance increases, while stress arising from obstacles is inversely proportional to job performance or decreased performance.

Technical Implementation Unit for Food Crops and Horticulture Protection (UPT PTPH) on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Pangkalan Masyur Medan City is a government agency tasked with assisting the Head of Service in the implementation of administrative administration and/or technical duties of plant protection in the field of observation and control of Plant Destruction Organisms (OPT) as well as observation and handling of Climate Change Impacts (DPI) in all districts/cities. According to the results of an initial survey conducted by researchers at UPT PTPH that the results of employee performance appraisals from 2019 to 2020 showed a decrease in employee performance even though they almost averaged almost perfect scores, which was above 95% which was a very good percentage but still lower than in previously.

According to the results of interviews with UPT PTPH employees, what caused the decline in employee performance was the readiness of employees to face change. Changes that occur are in the work system and technology used to support work, especially at this time the Covid 19 Pandemic is also happening which requires every employee to be ready to face the impact of the Covid 19 Pandemic. The application of a new work system with working from home methods and systems reporting activities online, online attendance and virtual meetings even during the pandemic there is training via online or virtual so that employees are required to be ready to face these changes. However, the readiness to change employees is not only required because of the pandemic but also because of changes that occur in the organization. The online activity and attendance reporting system was actually planned before the Covid 19 pandemic occurred, to support technological change, which has now entered the 4.0 industrial revolution. which requires employees to be more technology literate.

In addition, changes due to the Covid 19 pandemic that occurred even though they were only temporary or did not last long, they still had to be the attention of the agency so that when there were problems that were almost the same as the covid 19 pandemic. The agency had prepared preventive and handling measures to support the work of employees so that employees also employee self-awareness can be built early in order to be able to face changes in the future.

The readiness of employees in dealing with changes that occur in the agency can be seen from the results of the pre-survey on 20 UPT PTPH employees:

Table 1. Results of Pre-Survey Variable Readiness to Change Employees

	Statement	Answer		Number of Employees
		No	Yes	
1	I believe the changes that have occurred are the right decisions for the agency.	5	15	20
2	I'm sure I'll be able to implement the changes.	15	5	20
3	I'm sure there will be institutional support for change.	10	10	20
4	I'm sure I can keep up with changes made by the agency.	12	8	20

Based on the results of the pre-survey, it shows that in the first point there are 15 people who answered with the choice of "Yes" that the employee believes the changes made by the agency are the right decisions. However, in the second statement there were 15 employees who answered the statement with the choice of "No" that the employee was still not sure that he would be able to implement the changes. The third statement has the same number of answers on the choices "Yes" and "No" where 10 employees feel confident about the agency's support and 10 other employees feel unsure about the agency's support for change. However, in the statement, the four employees answered the choice of "No" as many as 12 people where employees were still not sure they could follow the changes that occurred in the agency. These results show that there is a lack of readiness to change in employees. This result can also cause a decrease in employee performance. In accordance with the research results of Asbari, et.al (2021), readiness to change has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The same result was also stated by Novitasari (2021), readiness to change has a positive and significant effect on worker performance. This shows that readiness to change is one of the causes of an agency's performance to decline.

The next variable which is one that affects employee performance is OCB. The results of interviews with employees of UPT PTPH, researchers found that OCB at UPT PTPH has not been realized properly. According to employees, the awareness of employees in carrying out or participating in activities that are outside the written description is still very small so that superiors still have to give directions or invites to their employees to carry out and participate in these activities.

The researcher also noticed when visiting the UPT PTPH office that there were still employees who had to be given direction to help their co-workers when the co-worker was not present at the office. The absence of co-workers at the office is caused by WFH so that there are tasks that should be done by the co-workers that cannot be done because the required data is in the office and is not stored in softcopy or files on the computer. In addition, the researcher also saw that in doing their work, there were some employees who still complained because of the tasks given. This is also supported by the results of a pre-survey conducted on 20 employees working at UPT PTPH as follows:

Table 2. Pre Survey Results Organization Citizenship Behavior Variables

	Statement	Answer		Number of Employees
		No	Yes	
1	Helping do the work of colleagues who are unable to attend the agency.	5	15	20
2	Arrive at the agency 20 minutes earlier or before work hours.	12	8	20
3	Think from the positive side to solve work problems that occur in the agency without giving complaints to the agency.	11	9	20
4	Participate in every activity held by the agency.	11	9	20

Based on the results of the pre-survey, it can be seen that in Table 1.3 in point number 1 there are 15 employees who answered "Yes" to help do the work of colleagues who were unable to attend the agency. This shows that there are still many employees who want to help their co-workers who cannot attend the agency. However, something different was obtained in point number 2, which had 12 employees who answered "No" where there were still many employees who

did not show up 20 minutes earlier. Although during the interview it was found that no one was late, the time for attendance was only 10 or 5 minutes before the check-in time. The next point number 3 shows that there are 11 employees who answered "No" where employees still often complain in solving existing problems. In addition, point 4 shows that sportsmanship is still lacking, namely there are still many who complain about work when there are problems in their duties or work. This is indicated by the presence of 11 employees who answered "No" to the statement to take part in the activities held by the agency.

The results obtained from these points can be seen that UPT employees are still lacking in implementing OCB in agencies so that there needs to be an increase in the OCB behavior of UPT PTPH employees. Because based on the facts found, it shows that agencies with employees who have implemented good OCB will get better work performance when compared to other agencies in the same family that do not apply OCB (Robbins & Judge, 2013). This is in line with the results of research conducted by Al-Mahasneh (2015), Talagheni & Sabokro (2016), Yuniarto (2018) and Lestari & Ghaby (2018), that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has a positive and significant effect on work performance. However, there are differences in the results of research conducted by Astuti and Oktaria (2018), and Mustika and Surjayanti (2018) that OCB does not have a significant effect on performance.

Employee performance can also be affected due to work stress on employees. According to the results of an interview with one of the employees, the work stress shown by employees is feeling worried about the changes that are happening right now, especially because of the COVID 19 pandemic. Employees feel less enthusiastic because of the workload that is too much coupled with the Covid 19 pandemic which requires employees to work from home and apply strict PROKES during work. In addition, changes are also the cause of increased stress levels for UPT PTPH employees. Where the work system is changing and reporting activities and attendance is done online, employees who are used to doing everything manually have to learn how to do all activity and attendance reporting with an online system. In addition to the pressure of having to learn new things because of these changes, employees also feel anxious because of the lack of facilities and have to adapt to the use of technology where according to the interviewees, many employees over the age of 40 find it more difficult to adjust to changes in technology so that reporting shifts from manual. going online makes the employee depressed. Another pressure felt by employees is the difficulty of the internet network which is a necessity that employees need to send reports and employee attendance.

This can happen because employees are still not ready to deal with existing changes and the behavior of employees is still low in carrying out extra activities to be able to improve the performance of their own employees and the performance of the company or agency. The following are the results of a pre-survey of 20 UPT PTPH employees in seeing work stress:

Table 3. Pre-Survey Results of Employee Work Stress

	Statement	Answer		Number of Employees
		No	Yes	
1	Limited information at work makes me feel worried during work.	10	10	20
2	I feel my workload is too heavy.	10	10	20
3	The facilities I need while working are still inadequate, so I get anxious easily.	9	11	20
4	The time allotted to complete the task stresses me out.	7	13	20
5	The development of technology used at work makes it difficult for me to adapt.	7	13	20

Based on the results of the pre-survey above, it can be seen that there is work stress on employees at UPT PTPH because in Table 1.4, there are 3 statement points getting the answer "Yes" but more than half of the employees who answered the pre-survey questionnaire for choices that employees answered with the choice " Yes". Statement point number 3 obtained the answer "Yes" as many as 11 people where employees feel anxious because the facilities needed during work are still inadequate. The next statement points get a "Yes" answer as many as 13 employees, namely a statement about the time given by the agency in completing the task makes employees feel pressured and worried. The statement answered with "Yes" as many as 13 employees is that the development of technology used in work makes employees find it difficult to adapt. As explained earlier that this is also influenced by employees who are in the age range of 40 years and over so that employees are still difficult to accept and adapt to changes. This shows that UPT PTPH employees experience stress during work, mainly due to changes and demands from behavior outside the job description which will ultimately lead to a decrease in UPT PTPH employee performance. According to Tavakoli (2014) that change can cause distress and can lead to resistance to changes that occur. Distress or negative stress that arises will harm employees and agencies.

Another variable that affects stress is OCB. According to Hendrawan (2020) high OCB can reduce work stress on employees so that organizational goals can be achieved, namely optimal performance. Differences of opinion were found in the research of Belogolovsky and Somech (2010), that high OCB will cause conflict and role ambiguity for employees so that it can lead to perceptions of stress in the workplace. In addition, OCB behavior according to Deery, et.al (2016) can confiscate greater personal expenses.

Ayatse and Inkyanyon (2012) also have the same opinion, that OCB has a positive and significant effect on work stress. This means that every increase in OCB behavior carried out by employees will increase work stress on employees. stress that arises in employees in the end if it lasts for a long time will result in a decrease in employee performance which will affect the company.

Therefore, it is necessary for agencies to pay attention to the level of stress owned by employees because it can affect employee performance such as the results of research obtained by Pranata, et.al (2020), Kristanti and Lestari (2019), Noermijatie & Primasari (2015) and Susiarti, et al. al (2019) that work stress has a negative and significant effect on work performance. Different from the results obtained by previous researchers which showed a negative effect on performance, while in Pandey's (2020) research, job stress had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, which means that high work stress will also increase employee performance.

Based on the phenomenon that has been described previously, the researcher became interested in examining the readiness of employees to change Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) on employee work performance through work stress on employees of UPT PTPH on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Masyur Base in Medan City.

II. Methodology

This type of research is associative, namely research that intends to describe and test hypotheses knowing the relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2017). This research was conducted on employees of UPT Protection of Food Crops and Horticulture (PTPH) on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Medan Masyur Base. It is carried out from September 2021 to December 2021. The population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that become certain quantities and characteristics that are applied by researchers to study and draw conclusions (Sugiono, 2012). The population in this study were all permanent employees of UPT PTPH, amounting to 91 people.

The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiono, 2012: 116). The sampling technique used is probability sampling technique. The probability technique used is simple random sampling where every employee has the same rights to be the sample in the study. This study uses a Likert scale. The Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena, this has been specifically determined by researchers, hereinafter referred to as research variables Sugiyono, (2008:132).

The data collection methods used in this study are:

1. Interview (Interview) which is to conduct direct questions and answers to respondents, namely employees of UPT PTPH on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Medan Masyur Base. Regarding the information or information needed in this research.
2. Using the questionnaire method (question list) related to employee's readiness to change, OCB, job stress and employee performance. The questionnaire given is a closed questionnaire where respondents are only given the opportunity to choose the answers that have been provided according to their opinions, namely by providing a number of written questions that are used to obtain information from respondents.
3. Documentation study is to collect secondary data at UPT PTPH on Jl. AH. Nasution No. 4 Pangkalan Masyur Medan, such as the number of employees, job descriptions, employee performance, and others related to research.

This study uses a variance-based structural equation model / SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Square) with SmartPLS version 3. SEM is one method that has been developed to cover the shortcomings of the regression analysis method. The regression method itself is the method most often used by quantitative researchers (Hussein, 2015). Mahmud and Ratmono (2013) stated that the development of SEM has been divided into two types, namely covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and variance-based SEM or partial least squares (SEM-PLS).

Ghozali (2014:10) explains that PLS is an analytical method that is soft modeling because it is not based on the assumption that the data must be on a measurement scale, distribution of data (distribution free) and a certain number of samples, which means the number of samples can be small (under 100 samples). According to Ghazali (2012), the data used does not have to have a multivariate normal distribution (indicators with categorical, ordinal, interval to ratio scales can be used in the same model), the sample does not have to be large. This makes research easier because it is more flexible.

The purpose of SEM-PLS according to Ghozali & Latan (2015), is to develop a theory or build a theory (prediction orientation). PLS is used to explain whether there is a relationship between latent variables (prediction).

The path diagram provides an explanation of the pattern of relationships between latent variables and indicators. In addition, the path diagram also shows the relationship between causal pathways to endogenous and exogenous variables (Ghozali & Latan, 2015)

Figure 1. PLS SEM Path Diagram

Path analysis is also used to determine the direct and indirect effects of the observed variables. The path diagram depicting the pattern of relationships between variables in this study is to test and find out how big the causal relationship is between the variable Readiness to change employees (X1), and OCB (X2), on Employee Performance (Y) through work stress (Z). Sugiyono (2013) states that testing the independent variables on the dependent variable can be tested with a 95% confidence level for $e = 5\%$ 95% confidence level for $= 5\%$.

Testing on SEM PLS begins with testing the outer model which will measure construct validity and instrument reliability. The construct validity test in PLS was carried out through convergent validity, discriminant validity, and average extract (AVE) tests.

Convergent validity or convergent validity of the external model with the indicator reflective model is assessed based on the correlation between item scores/component scores and construct scores calculated by PLS. The reflective measure is said to be high if it has a correlation of more than 0.70 with the construct to be measured. However, for research in the early stages of developing a measurement scale, a loading value of 0.5 to 0.60 is considered sufficient (Chin, 1997 in Hartono and Abdillah, 2014: 61).

The discriminant validity of the measurement model with reflective indicators was assessed based on the cross loading of the measurement with the construct. The latent construct predicts block size better than other block sizes if the correlation of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the correlation with other constructs.

Another method to assess discriminant validity is to compare the square root value of the average variance extract (AVE) of each construct with the correlations between other constructs in the model. If the AVE root value of each construct is greater than the correlation value between the construct and other constructs in the model, it is said to have a good discriminant validity value. The recommended AVE value must be greater than 0.50 (Fornell and Lacker, 1981 in Ghozali, 2014: 40).

The next measurement is to see the reliability of the research. Measurements that can be used to measure the reliability of the component score of latent variables and the results are more conservative than the composite reliability measure. Composite reliability measures the real value in the reliability of a construct and is better for estimating the internal consistency of a construct (Salisbury et al., 2002 in Hartono and Abdillah, 2014:62). Cronbach's alpha measures

the lower limit of the reliability value of a construct. The rule of thumb is that the value of alpha or composite reliability must be greater than 0.7, although a value of 0.6 is still acceptable (Hair et al., 2006 Hartono and Abdillah, 2014: 62).

Inner Model (inner relation, structural model, and substantive theory) describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. Inner model is a structural model to predict causality between latent variables. In the inner model, it can also be seen the collinearity of data between variables. This collinearity is used as one of the prerequisite tests in SEM (Ghozali: 2010: 36). Through the bootstrapping process, T-statistic test parameters were obtained to predict the existence of a causal relationship. The structural model (inner model) was evaluated by looking at the percentage of variance explained by the R² value for the dependent variable using the Stone-Geisser Q-square test (Kalnadi 2013) and also looking at the magnitude of the structural path coefficient.

The structural model was evaluated using R-square for the dependent construct, Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive relevance, and t-test and significance of structural path parameter coefficients. Changes in the value of R² can be used to assess the effect of certain independent latent variables on the dependent latent variable whether it has a substantive effect (Ghozali, 2014:42). The result of R² is 0.67; 0.33; and 0.19 indicates that the model is "good", "moderate", and "weak" (Chin, 1998).

The PLS model was also evaluated by looking at the predictive Q-square of relevance by the model as well as its parameter estimates. The Q-square value > 0 indicates the model has predictive relevance, on the other hand if the Q-square value 0 indicates the model lacks predictive relevance (Chin, 1998).

The magnitude of Q² has a value with a range of $0 < Q^2 < 1$, where the closer to 1 means the better. According to Sarwono (2006), to facilitate interpretation, it is made as follows:

- a. 0 : There is no correlation between the two variables
- b. >0 - 0.25: Very weak correlation
- c. >0.25 - 0.5: Correlation is sufficient
- d. >0.5 - 0.75: Strong correlation
- e. >0.75 - 0.99: Very strong correlation
- f. 1: Perfect correlation

This f-square test was conducted to determine the goodness of the model. The f-square values of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 can be interpreted as whether the latent variable predictor has a weak, medium, or large influence on the structural level (Ghozali, 2011).

t test

The next test is to see the significance of the effect between variables by looking at the parameter coefficient values and the statistical significance value of T, namely through the bootstrapping method (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

- a. If Tcount Ttable at 95% level or = 5%, the hypothesis in this study is accepted.
- b. If Tcount Ttable at 95% level or = 5%, the hypothesis in this study is rejected.

To determine the value of tTable, the significance level of is determined with degrees of freedom $df = (n - k)$ where n is the number of observations. Indirect effect testing is done by using the bootstrapping method using smartPLS. In this study there is an intervening variable, namely work stress. Intervening variables are said to be able to mediate the effect of exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables if the T statistic value is greater than the T table and the P value is smaller than the significant level used (5%).

III. Results

Structural Equation Modeling

Outer Model

The outer model in PLS SEM has parts, namely construct validity and instrument reliability. Construct validity consists of convergent validity, discriminant validity and average extracted (AVE). As for the reliability of the instrument, it can be seen from composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha (CA). The following is the result of processed data from SmartPLS to measure the construct validity of the data generated on the outer loading to see convergent validity or the validity of each indicator used.

Table 4. Validity Test Results Convergent Based on Loading Factor

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor
X1 -Readiness to Change Employees	X1.1	0.787
	X1.2	0.839
	X1.3	0.805
	X1.4	0.769
	X1.5	0.752
	X1.6	0.906
	X1.7	0.783
	X1.8	0.870
	X1.9	0.777
	X1.10	0.816
	X1.11	0.842
	X1.12	0.784
X2 - OCB	X2.1	0.781
	X2.2	0.804
	X2.3	0.793
	X2.4	0.806
	X2.5	0.816
	X2.6	0.787
	X2.7	0.862
	X2.8	0.813
	X2.9	0.819
	X2.10	0.828
Z- Work Stress	Z1	0.794
	Z2	0.823
	Z3	0.795
	Z4	0.820
	Z5	0.839
	Z6	0.791
	Z7	0.836
	Z8	0.830
	Z9	0.849
	Z10	0.797
Y - Employee Performance	Y1	0.779
	Y2	0.807
	Y3	0.850
	Y4	0.855
	Y5	0.852
	Y6	0.855
	Y7	0.855

Figure 2. Outer Loading Diagram (Loading Factor)

Table 4 shows that all indicators contained in each variable used in this study are <0.7 , which means this indicates that all indicator statement items used are valid or meet the validity requirements such as the opinion of Ghazali and Latan (2015) that convergent validity meets rule in measurement with loading factor if > 0.7 . Furthermore, to see other validity tests on the SEM-PLS, namely by looking at the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value.

Table 5. Validity Test Results based on AVE

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X1 -Readiness to Change Employees	0,659
X2 - OCB	0,658
y -Employee Performance	0,700
Z -Work Stress	0,669

Figure 3. Ave Grafik Graph

Based on the results obtained in Table 5, the AVE value in the X1-readiness variable changed by 0.659, the X2-OCB variable was 0.658, the Y variable was 0.700 and the Z-work stress variable was 0.669. This shows that the AVE value of each variable used in this study has met the validity for the variable, which is above 0.5 (> 0.5). According to Ghazali and Latan (2015) a study is declared valid based on the AVE if the value obtained is > 0.5. The same thing was stated by Hair, et.al. (2011) stated that the AVE value for each good construct was at least 0.5. Furthermore, after getting the AVE value, it can also be seen the discriminant validity in this study as in the Fornel Larcker Criterion table as follows:

Table 6. Discriminant Validity Test Results

	X1 - Readiness to change employees	X2 - OCB	Y - Employee performance	Z - Work stress
X1 - Readiness to change employees	0,812			
X2 - OCB	0,718	0,811		
Y - Employee performance	0,557	0,382	0,837	
Z - Work stress	0,408	0,221	0,040	0,818

The results of discriminant validity which can be seen from Table 6 show that the value of the square root of the AVE of a variable is greater than the correlation value with that variable with other variables such as the X1-X1 variable which is 0.812 which is greater than the X1-X2 variable of 0.718, greater also from the X1-Y construct variable which has a value of 0.557, and it is also greater than X1-Z which is 0.408. Likewise for other variables so that it can be stated that this study has good discriminant validity. In addition to measurements on validity, measurements for reliability tests are also carried out which can be seen from Cronbach's Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability. The following table shows the results of the reliability test based on the CA and Composite Reliability values:

Table 7. Composite Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
X1 - Readiness to change employees	0,953	0,959
X2 - OCB	0,943	0,951
y - Employee performance	0,929	0,942
Z - Work stress	0,946	0,960

Figure 4. Composite Reliability

Figure 5. Cronbach’s Alpha (CA)

Table 7 shows the CA in each variable such as in the X1 variable at 0.953, for X2 at 0.943, Y at 0.929 and Z at 0.946. The results of the processed data indicate that each variable used is >0.7. This means that the variables used in this study are reliable or prove the accuracy, consistency, and accuracy of the instrument in measuring constructs.

Table 7 also contains the results of Composite Reliability, which is also one of the test results to see the reliability of the research. The results obtained indicate that each variable is greater than 0.7 as in X1 of 0.959, X2 of 0.951, Y of 0.942 and Z of 0.953. These results also prove that the variables used in this study are reliable and can prove accuracy and consistency as well as accuracy in measuring variables.

Inner Model

The next stage in the analysis using SEM PLS, namely the Inner model, can be done by looking at the test results:

1. R Square Test

To measure the level of variation in the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, the R2 test was carried out. The following is a R Square table obtained from the results of data processing from SmartPLS:

Table 8. R Square

	<i>R Square</i>
y - Employee performance	0,352
Z -Work stress	0,178

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that the R Square for the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y) is 0.352 or 35.2%, meaning that the employee performance variable can be explained by the variable readiness to change employees (X1), OCB (X2), and work stress (Z).) to the performance of 35.2% and the rest is influenced by other variables outside of this study.

For the work stress variable (Z), the R Square value is 17.8%, which means that the variable readiness to change employees (X1) and OCB (X2) can affect the work stress variable by 17.8%. According to Chin (1998), the result of R2 is 0.67; 0.33; and 0.19 indicates that the model is “good” , “moderate or moderate”, and “weak” . So it can be concluded that for R2 the employee performance variable is in the moderate or moderate category, while the work stress variable is in the weak category.

2. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at two influences, namely the direct and indirect effects of this study. The following is a table of direct influence test results with significance in this study:

Table 9. Direct Effect

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STDEV DV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Readiness to change employees(X1) » Employee performance(Y)	0,698	0,714	0,168	4,156	0,000
Readiness to change employees(X1) » Work Stress (Z)	0,516	0,528	0,190	2,716	0,007
OCB (X2) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,069	-0,040	0,187	0,372	0,710
OCB (X2) » Work Stress (Z)	-0,150	-0,139	0,172	0,847	0,382
Work Stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,224	-0,231	0,112	1,993	0,045

Based on the results obtained in Table 9, it can be seen that the direct influence of each variable used in this research is as follows:

Employee readiness to change has a positive effect on work stress with a value of 0.516 and significant with a P Value of 0.007 <0.05. These results answer the hypothesis in this study that Hypothesis 1:

H0 is rejected. because there is no negative effect between the variables of employee readiness to change and work stress.

H1 is accepted because there is a positive and significant effect of the employee's readiness to change variables on the work stress variable.

Employee readiness to change has a positive effect on employee performance with a value of 0.698 in the Original Sample (O) column which is the path coefficient on the test results and is significant with a p value <0.05, which is 0.000. These results answer the hypothesis in this study that Hypothesis 2:

H0 is "accepted" because there is a positive and significant influence between the variables of employee readiness to change on employee performance.

H1 is rejected because readiness to change employees has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

OCB has a negative effect on work stress with a path coefficient value of -0.150 but not significant with a p value > 0.05, which is 0.382. These results answer the hypothesis in this study that Hypothesis 3:

H0 is rejected, namely OCB has a positive but not significant effect on work stress.

H1 is accepted, namely OCB has a positive and significant effect on work stress

OCB has a negative effect on employee performance with a path coefficient value of -0.069 but not significant with a p value > 0.05, which is 0.710. These results answer the hypothesis in this study that Hypothesis 4:

H0 is rejected, namely OCB has a positive and not significant effect on employee performance.

H1 is accepted, namely OCB has a negative effect on employee performance.

Work stress has a negative effect on employee performance with a value of -0.224 and significant with a p value of 0.045 <0.05. These results answer the hypothesis in this study that Hypothesis 5

H0 is accepted, namely work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance.

H1 is rejected, that is, work stress has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

Furthermore, testing the hypothesis with an indirect effect between the independent variable (readiness to change and OCB) and the dependent variable (employee performance) through mediating or intervening variables (work stress). As shown in the following table:

Table 10. Indirect Effect

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STEDV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Readiness to change employees(X1) » Work stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,115	-0,121	0,079	1,468	0,142
OCB (X2) » Work stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	0,034	0,034	0,048	0,695	0,487

Based on Table 10 for hypothesis testing by looking at the indirect effect, namely as follows:

Employee readiness to change is not mediated by work stress to affect performance because the results in Table 10 show that it is negative (-0.115) and not significant where the significance is greater than 0.05, which is 0.142, so for Hypothesis 6

H0 is accepted, that is, there is no work stress from the readiness to change employees on employee performance.

H1 is rejected, namely there is a mediating effect of work stress from employee readiness to change on employee performance.

OCB is mediated by work stress leading to employee performance but the effect given is not significant because the p value is greater than 0.05 so for Hypothesis 7

H0 is accepted, that is, there is no mediating effect of work stress from OCB on employee performance.

H1 is rejected, that is, there is a mediating effect of work stress from OCB on employee performance. Furthermore, in the following table it can be clearly seen that the direct and indirect effects on this research are as follows:

Table 11. Direct and Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STEDV)	P Values
Readiness to change employees (X1) » Employee performance(Y)	0,698	0,714	0,168	4,156	0,000
Readiness to change employees (X1) » Work stress (Z)	0,516	0,528	0,190	2,716	0,007
OCB (X2) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,069	-0,040	0,187	0,372	0,710
OCB (X2) » Work stress (Z)	-0,150	-0,139	0,172	0,847	0,382
Work stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,224	-0,231	0,112	1,993	0,045
Readiness to change employees(X1) » Work stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	-0,115	-0,121	0,079	1,468	0,142
OCB (X2) » Work stress (Z) » Employee performance(Y)	0,034	0,034	0,048	0,695	0,487

Based on Table 11 that employee readiness to change has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, readiness to change has a positive and significant effect on work stress, OCB has a negative but not significant effect on employee performance, OCB has a negative but not significant effect on work stress, work stress has a negative effect and significant impact on employee performance, readiness to change has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance through work stress, and OCB has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance through work stress.

IV. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter regarding readiness to change employees and OCB on employee performance through work stress at UPT PTPH North Sumatra, it can be concluded: Readiness to change employees has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The employee's readiness to change has a negative and significant effect on work stress. Employee OCB has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance. OCB has a negative and significant effect on work stress. Job stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance. Readiness to change employees has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance through work stress. OCB has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance through work stress.

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions above, the researchers provide suggestions to UPT PTPH North Sumatra and further researchers as follows: Based on the results obtained that in improving performance it is necessary to have readiness to change employees. The readiness to change employees at UPT PTPH affects performance so it needs to be improved again. However, what needs to be considered is that UPT PTPH in implementing changes must review the age of employees because employees who are more than 50 years old will have a longer responsiveness so that there needs to be initial training both in terms of practice and psychology in supporting changes and mentoring at the beginning. implementation of changes. So that performance can be maintained. In particular, what needs to be paid attention to is the indicator that changes will not hinder careers, agencies support employees in changing and clearly describe to employees the reasons and benefits of the agency with changes so that employees also become more prepared to follow changes. OCB at UPT PTPH must also be maintained and not to make employees feel that OCB which is usually done with pleasure becomes a burden, causing stress and lowering performance. especially on the point of participating in activities held by the agency and being positive in work and the tasks given are always completed which have a small value compared to others in descriptive analysis. Because the activities outside the job desk are numerous and require costs that make employees burdened if the costs are large and do not receive compensation from the agency. The task that is given is basically an employee's obligation, but if the task

given is outside the job desk, the employee must be able to complete it if it has been given. Employee job stress is the variable with the lowest average descriptive analysis so it must be paid attention to because there are still UPT PTPH employees who answer doubtfully and disagree and strongly disagree, especially on the indicators of headaches, fatigue, unstable blood pressure because thinking about work, irritability because communication is difficult to establish, work pressure lowers concentration, irritability and procrastination. Work stress can be maintained by helping each other and there is no communication cut off or misunderstanding, it must be discussed and discussed, especially between divisions, must be able to work together, give appreciation for the hard work of employees who have reached the target faster than the deadline, etc. Researchers have limited time and money so that researchers can only use variables of readiness to change and OCB on performance through work stress. Suggestions for further researchers to be able to add independent variables such as leadership, incentives or work environment both physical and non-physical or to add intervening variables such as job satisfaction and morale and increase the number of respondents studied. Because the larger the sample, the more significant the results obtained.

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